

Modeling Human Perceptual Hysteresis via Transformer-based Solutions

Jason G. Hwang

Cherry Creek High School

May 7, 2026

Abstract

Modeling human perceptual hysteresis through CNN solutions failed to fully address first frame misclassifications. These initial misclassifications can propagate to next frames, compounding the difficulty of radiologists to determine whether the model is incorrectly modeling hysteresis or suffering from first frame errors. By taking advantage of global attention in Vision Transformers (ViTs), my proposed model resolves first frame misclassifications through superior discrimination of lines in shapes and extraneous lines. However, the inaccurate hysteresis produced by ViT based models when compared to previous CNN models suggest a need for in-depth comparison between deep learning based hysteresis approaches and widely known hysteresis models in the computational neuroscience field.

Introduction

At an introductory glance, human perceptual hysteresis, which is also known as serial dependence in human perception is defined as previous stimuli (i.e. images) influencing the interpretation of the current stimulus (Pascucci et al., 2023). Figure 1 illustrates this phenomenon.

Figure 1. A sequence of images transforms the man's face to the woman kneeling (You et al., 2011). If a person classifies the images from left to right, they might classify later images of the kneeling woman as a man's face because of prior perception of the man's face influencing their interpretation of following images.

Perceptual hysteresis is a key problem for radiologists when they identify cancer in x-ray scans (Ren et al., 2023). For example, if previous scans displayed benign tumors, the radiologists may classify the next scan as benign (even though it may be malignant) because their perception is unconsciously biased towards the previous benign case. Hence, an accurate hysteresis model that can find a sequence of images without any hysteresis is of great interest.

Although, in my previous research publication, I trained hysteresis models such as ResNet-LSTMs that successfully mimicked hysteresis, they suffered from first frame errors such as first frame image misclassifications (Hwang, 2026). In my previous paper, I concluded that repetition padding, where the first image is processed repeatedly before analyzing later images, might address this problem. However, after more testing, I determined that repetition padding failed to completely resolve first frame (image) misclassifications.

First frame misclassifications are a problem for radiologists because incorrect predictions can propagate into the prediction for the next frame, thereby causing many initial images to be misclassified. If many of the first images are misclassified, radiologists will struggle to determine whether the model is incorrectly modeling hysteresis or the model is suffering from first frame errors.

By analyzing the first frame images the model misclassifies, the model confuses fine-grained lines as 3D shapes, suggesting that the model struggles to differentiate between lines that make up semantic shapes and non-essential lines. A transformer approach seems promising in

resolving this problem by introducing a global context, which allows the model to compare features like lines across the entire image (Dosovitskiy et al., 2021).

Methodology

In the context of AI, transformers are a type of model that uses self-attention to learn the important parts or features of data. These features are like the summary of each image. For reference, the capital “T” in ChatGPT stands for transformers.

The model I will compare transformers with is a Temporal Convolutional Neural Network (TCN). A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) convolves or filters out the useful features of each image. Then, the TCN compares the extracted features across different images to accurately predict each image. From testing, I concluded that TCNs are a more suitable model than ResNet-LSTMs, the model I used in my first paper, because TCNs are easier to train and produce more consistent results.

While there are many types of transformers, I will focus on Vision Transformers (ViTs) because of its strengths in understanding global context. Despite the strengths of modern ViTs, the first implementations of ViTs exhibited limited advantages over older CNN based models.

Dosovitskiy et al.’s findings showed that ViTs, when trained on large datasets, can perform on par or slightly better compared to traditional CNNs such as ResNets (Dosovitskiy et al., 2021). However, they demonstrate that ViTs show poor performance compared to CNNs when trained on small datasets, such as the IllusionBench dataset I use for modeling hysteresis (Hemmat et al., 2024). They conclude that the reason for little to no performance gains is due to how ViTs have

fewer built-in inductive biases for image structure, such as locality and translation equivariance. To remedy this deficiency, there has been much research into training specialized ViTs such as Swin, I-JEPA, ConvTransformer, etc. The specific transformer model I tested is a ConvTransformer (Liu et al., 2020). ConvTransformers feature locality bias by filtering through CNNs before and after the transformer stage, which alleviates the issue of having few inductive biases.

The two models I tested are a TCN and a ConvTransformer. At the beginning of each model, an EfficientNet, which is a type of CNN, filters out important details of each image. These features are then processed by a TCN or a ConvTransformer. The final layer was changed for binary classification, and the two categories or classes of images were museum or animal.

I used the PyTorch library for easy access to TCN and ConvTransformer frameworks. The dataset used is the IllusionBench dataset, which is a highly ambiguous dataset with 2 categories or classes of data that is suitable for modeling human perceptual hysteresis (Hemmat et al., 2024). Only the museum dataset is used. The size of the images is reduced to 512 by 512 before being processed, and the AdamW optimizer was used for training.

Similar to my previous paper, the test data will be represented in a graph. The x-axis of the graph represents the frame or index number that spans the set of integers 1 to 8. The y-axis represents the average prediction value, which is a probability from 0 to 1. For each index, the mean probability \pm standard deviation will be plotted.

To quantify the performance of each model, the standard deviation of the first frame will determine the severity of first frame misclassifications. A higher standard deviation for the first frame will indicate increased first frame misclassifications while a standard deviation of 0 will indicate no first frame misclassifications.

To determine the accuracy of the hysteresis for each model, the “normalized error” will be calculated by taking the difference between the ideal prediction and the test prediction for each index. Taking the sum of the normalized error for each frame gives the total normalized error. A higher total normalized error means a less accurate hysteresis and a total normalized error of 0 means a perfectly accurate hysteresis. The ideal prediction of each frame is represented by the ideal prediction graph. The ideal prediction graph was theorized based on my previous experience with modeling hysteresis. The averaged hysteresis effect across various models and datasets yielded Figure 2.

Figure 2. Representation of ideal prediction graph. The x-axis represents the index number (1-8), and the y-axis represented the probability from 0 to 1.

Results

Figure 2. Test graph for TCN.

Figure 3. Test graph for transformer.

The total normalized error for the temporal CNN model is 0.56. The total normalized error for the transformer model is 1.70.

The standard deviation of the first frame for the TCN is 0.33 while the standard deviation of the first frame for the transformer is 0.03.

Discussion

Beginning with the strengths of the transformer model, the lower standard deviation on the first frame indicates that the model produces much less first frame errors. In fact, the standard deviation is negligible, meaning that transformers completely resolve first frame errors. The resolution of first frame errors suggests that the spatial attention of transformers helps feature discrimination, decreasing first frame errors.

However, the cost of this ideal performance for the first frame is the much less accurate hysteresis compared to TCNs. This is shown by how the total normalized error is much larger for transformers. This means the practical use cases of transformer models to model hysteresis is limited for radiologists.

As for the limitations of the study, the IllusionBench dataset isn't ideal for modeling hysteresis. This is due to how there are abrupt changes in details and objects in the IllusionBench dataset. In comparison, the man's face to kneeling woman data has much smaller changes in details that induce a gradual change in perception. You et al.'s success on modeling hysteresis with the man's face to kneeling woman data is an indication that the IllusionBench dataset may not reproduce similar hysteresis using the models that You et al. used (spiking neural network and

slow dynamic system). This is especially true because spiking neural networks and slow dynamic systems are conventional in modeling neurobiological processes such as human perceptual hysteresis while deep learning has only started to show success. The limitation of the IllusionBench dataset means that the actual amount of hysteresis of each sequence might vary significantly from the ideal prediction values. This could mean that transformers are modeling hysteresis more accurately compared to TCNs.

The issue of the unsubstantiated ideal hysteresis graph may be resolved by comparing transformers and TCNs to existing models that are known to accurately model hysteresis like the spiking neural networks and slow dynamic systems verified by You et al.

Conclusion

Although transformers resolve first frame errors through better feature discrimination, they struggle at mimicking accurate hysteresis. This means that transformer models are less viable than TCNs at helping radiologists classify images without suffering from the hysteresis effect. Future research should look into comparing transformers and TCNs with expert verified hysteresis models such as the spiking neural network.

References

Dosovitskiy, A., Beyer, L., Kolesnikov, A., Weissenborn, D., Zhai, X., Unterthiner, T., Dehghani, M., Minderer, M., Heigold, G., Gelly, S., Uszkoreit, J., & Houlsby, N. (2021). An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale. *International Conference on Learning Representations*. <https://openreview.net/forum?id=YicbFdNTTy>

- Hemmat, A., Davies, A., Lamb, T. A., Yuan, J., Torr, P., Khakzar, A., & Pinto, F. (2024). Hidden in plain sight: Evaluating abstract shape recognition in vision-language models. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (Vol. 37). NeurIPS.
<https://doi.org/10.52202/079017-2808>
- Hwang, J. (2026). Learning human perceptual hysteresis via deep CNN-RNN networks. *International Journal of High School Research*, 8(6), 69–73.
<https://doi.org/10.36838/IJHSR86.69>
- Liu, Z., Luo, S., Li, W., Lu, J., Wu, Y., Sun, S., Li, C., & Yang, L. (2021). *ConvTransformer: A convolutional transformer network for video frame synthesis*. arXiv.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.10185>
- Pascucci, D., Tanrikulu, Ö. D., Ozkirli, A., Houborg, C., Ceylan, G., Zerr, P., Rafiei, M., & Kristjánsson, Á. (2023). Serial dependence in visual perception: A review. *Journal of vision*, 23(1), 9. <https://doi.org/10.1167/jov.23.1.9>
- Ren, Z., Canas-Bajo, T., Ghirardo, C., Manassi, M., Yu, S. X., & Whitney, D. (2023). Serial dependence in perception across naturalistic generative adversarial network-generated mammogram. *Journal of medical imaging (Bellingham, Wash.)*, 10(4), 045501.
<https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JMI.10.4.045501>
- You, H., Meng, Y., Huan, D., & Wang, D.-H. (2011). The neural dynamics for hysteresis in visual perception. *Neurocomputing*, 74(17), 3502–3508.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2011.06.004>